

LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE AS A SECOND LANGUAGE

Isanova Sayyora Ilhomovna

Student of Samarkand State Medical University, faculty of Dentistry

Shodikulova Aziza Zikirayayevna

PhD, Assistant teacher of Samarkand State Medical University, Uzbekistan

Abstract: English is an international language which is used officially all around the world. English can connect society with the full world. Everyone who wants to make connections with the world should learn English. In our country learn English is necessary to reach some targets. To make English as a second language in our life, we need to understand the basis of English and appropriate learning strategy. A lot of information in the world is written in English.

Key words: International language, learn English, second language,

Introduction. Today, English is international language. English language placed in multicultural and communication, in international business communication, and in international language of research. A lot of important information in the world is written in English.

More people in whole world know English language. English is a wonderful language; knowledge of this language gives you a chance to freely, actively and widely participate in the current community. People try and learn different language, but after their mother tongue stand as a second language for more people English is a second language. A second language age is any language that was acquired after their first. Knowing English is useful, it allows you communicate in different countries, makes travel interesting and unforgettable, helps you get job and promoted career advancement. In recent decades, scientists have found that the benefits of studying it are not limited to generally known facts. Moreover, people who are fluent in English live, as it were, in a different, highly cultural society, the boundaries of which are immeasurable wider. Knowledge of a language is no longer a luxury, but an urgent requirement of a new civilization. Also, most of the literature is written in English, and if you are a student, knowing English you can use these sources of information and it will be to your advantage. For instance, a lot of useful information for doctors is written in English sources.

The main goal of teaching a foreign language at the threshold level is the formation of communicative competence, where several components are distinguished:

linguistic competence, sociolinguistic, sociocultural competence, strategic, discursive and social competence. Since ancient times, language and speech have aroused comprehensive interest in study, being insufficiently studied problems due to their complexity and interconnectedness with the mental side of human life. The forerunner of psycholinguistics A.A. Leontiev names the German philosopher and linguist Wilhelm von Humboldt, because it was he who owned “the idea of speech activity and the understanding of language as a connecting link between society and man” (A.A. Leontiev). The subject of psycholinguistics is the relationship of personality with the structure and functions of speech activity, as well as language as the main element that forms the image of the human world.

The traditional phrase for non-native speakers of English using or studying the language in an English-speaking setting is “English as a second language” (sometimes known as “English for speakers of other languages”).

Second language learning in English. Additionally, language refers to specific methods of teaching language intended for people whom English is not their first language. To put it simply, language learning is the process by which the ability grows within a person. It takes strategies to learn a language, and strategies or procedures used by the students to process the information they were given.

We should learn English as a second language because at this time, English is an international language which is the language of communication to connect us with the development of the outside world. By mastering English, it gives us more opportunities to travel to various parts of the world without being hindered by communication. In addition, by learning English as a second language, it will give us more job opportunities so that we can follow developments in the outside world regarding future career.

Being proficient in English has become essential in this day and age. There can be certain challenges in certain nations when people are born with different mother tongues. When people speak in ordinary English, their responses occasionally still stutter, uneasy or possibly unrelated to discussions in English. For some whose mother tongue is not English, English can be challenging mostly because of its difficult to master syntax and unpredictable spelling. Furthermore, there are numerous terms in the English language that allegedly imply the same thing, naturally, some people may find this unclear or challenging. Those for whom English is not their mother tongue.

Moreover, per only spelling because pronunciation is where meaning is found, which can also confuse those acquiring English. Consequently, effective and enjoyable learning techniques are required when acquiring a second language in English.

Methods for learning English as a Second Language:

Firstly, you need to understand some points for learning,

Dictionary- is one of the important and fundamental parts when learning language, the beauty of your speech depends on your vocabulary.

Listening

Reading

Writing

Speaking

These skills are also important when learning English; each skill has its place.

"The aim of education should be to teach us rather how to think, than what to think"

Similar to the quote above, learning can occur as a result of the learners plans, behaviors, or routines when digesting the knowledge they have been given. We must include our learning outcomes with that citation. Using English as a second language in daily interactions. As an illustration, learning to write speaking and communicating in English by utilizing it and practicing it hearing abilities.

These days, with the advancement of technology, we can learn through social media, YouTube, online English learning programs, and other media in addition to books. Through using a few of these learning media, we will have a deeper understanding of the English-language content. Educating speaking English alongside native speakers not only boosts our self-confidence, but also enhances the standard of English language acquisition as a second language.

In recent years, the role of writing in teaching a foreign language has gradually increased, and, in a sense, writing is beginning to be considered as a reserve in increasing the effectiveness of teaching a foreign language. It is impossible not to take into account the practical significance of written speech communication in the light of modern means of communication, such as e-mail, the Internet, etc. In the latter case, writing as a type of verbal communication develops on the basis of only authentic material. Foreign internships for students, graduate students and young scientists require the ability to take notes in a foreign language, compose and fill out a

questionnaire, answer questionnaire questions, write an application for admission to study or work, write a short or detailed autobiography, write personal or business letters using the required form speech etiquette of native speakers, including a form of business etiquette.

Conclusion. Learning English as a second language after your native language is important. There are many positive aspects to learning English, since English is the world language today. If you want to learn English, set a goal and achieve it, learning the right skills. A lot of important information in the world is written in English.

References

1. Shodikulova, A. Z. (2021, December). The theory of an integrative approach to the analysis of the phenomenon of metonymy. In *Archive of Conferences* (pp. 56-57).
2. Shodikulova, A. Z. (2021). The text is about the phenomenon of cohesion. *Academicia Globe*, 2(05), 229-232.
3. Shodikulova, A. Z. (2022). The analysis of the phenomenon of metonymy. *Science and Education*, 3(12), 1136-1140.
4. Shodikulova, A. Z. (2021). Methodology For Using Computer Training Programs In English Lessons. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education (TURCOMAT)*, 12(13), 3358-3367.
5. Shodikulova, A. Z. (2021). COGNITIVE INTERPRETATION OF THE PHENOMENON OF METONYMY. *Scientific reports of Bukhara State University*, 5(1), 136-146.
6. Zikiryaevna, S. A. (2022). DISCURSIVE ANALYSIS OF DERIVED METONYMIE. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 1588-1592.
7. Zikiryaevna, S. A. (2022). Cognitive Interpretation Of The Phenomenon Of Metonymy. *Eurasian Medical Research Periodical*, 5, 102-104.
8. Шодикүлова, А. З. (2021). МЕДИАМАТНЛАРИНИНГ ЛИНГВИСТИК ТАДҚИҚИ МАСАЛАСИ. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 4(2).
9. Shodikulova, A. (2023). COHESIONS FORMED BY MEANS OF HYPONYMS. *Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры*, 3(9), 40-43.

10. SHODIKULOVA, A. Z. (2021). THE ROLE OF METONYMS IN THE FORMATION OF TEXT STRUCTURE. *THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE*
Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука, (9), 655-658.

11. Шодикулова, А. З. Asian journal of multidimensional research. *India (AJMRI) Vol, 9*, 151-152.

12. METONYMY, O. a teacher of department of languages, Medicine and Education faculty Samarkand State Medical Institute. *SCIENTIFIC REPORTS OF BUKHARA STATE UNIVERSITY*, 136(17), 49-52.

13. Шодикулова, А. З. (2023). АНТОНИМЛАР ВОСИТАСИДА ШАКЛЛАНАДИГАН МЕТОНИМИК КОГЕЗИЯ. *Research Focus International Scientific Journal*, 2(5), 80-84.

14. Шодикулова, А. З. (2023). СИНОНИМЛАР ВОСИТАСИДА ҲОСИЛ БЎЛАДИГАН МЕТОНОМИК КОГЕЗИЯ. *Journal of new century innovations*, 22(4), 60-63.

15. Shodikulova, A. (2023). COHESIONS FORMED BY MEANS OF NYRONYMS. *Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры*, 3(9), 40-43.

16. Шодикулова, А. З. (2022). Матнда когезия ходисаси. In *Конференция состоялась 5 марта 2022 года на базе Ташкентского государственного стоматологического института по адресу: Республика Узбекистан, 100047, г. Ташкент, ул. Махтумкули, 103. Цель конференции—знакомство и обмен опытом в обучении и в работе с цифровыми данными, технологиями их применения в гуманитарных* (p. 377).

17. Шодикулова, А. З. (2022). Матнда когезия ходисаси. In *Конференция состоялась 5 марта 2022 года на базе Ташкентского государственного стоматологического института по адресу: Республика Узбекистан, 100047, г. Ташкент, ул. Махтумкули, 103. Цель конференции—знакомство и обмен опытом в обучении и в работе с цифровыми данными, технологиями их применения в гуманитарных* (p. 377).

18. Шодикулова, А. З. (2021). Дискурсивный анализ производных метонимий. *Форум молодых ученых*, (4 (56)), 439-444.

19. Zikirayayevna, S. A. (2023). JAHON ADABIYOTI NAMOYONDASI JEYMS JOYS NIKOYALARI. " XXI ASRDA INNOVATION TEXNOLOGIYALAR,

FAN VA TA'LIM TARAQQIYOTIDAGI DOLZARB MUAMMOLAR" nomli respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi, 1(10), 123-125.

20. Zikiriyayevna, S. A. COGNITIVE-DISCURSIVE ASPECTS OF IMPLEMENTATION OF METONYMY IN A MEDIA.

21. Fomina Mayde Anatolevna, Shodikulova Aziza Zikiriyayevna. (2023). DEONTOLOGICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF WINGED SAYINGS IN MEDICINE. *Ethiopian International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 10(10), 124–125. R

22. CLASSIFICATION OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS by Saidova Kamola Ixomjanovna, Shodikulova Aziza Zikiriyayevna, <https://eprajournals.com/IJSR/article/2293>

23. Азиза Зикиряевна Шодикулова Когнитивная интерпретация феномена метонимии 241-243

24. Шодикулова Азиза Зикиряевна DISORDERS OF LIPID METABOLISM IN OBESE PEOPLE, *Science, Research, Development* 129-131.

25. Шодикулова Азиза Зикиряевна RHYTHMIC-STRUCTURAL DIVISION OF THE ENGLISH SPEECH (AS BASE OF THE CATEGORY OF INTRODUCTION) *Trans Asian Journal Impact FactorSJIF2020:6.882*.

26. Mukhamadiyeva, M., & Sharipov, B. (2022). LATIN AS THE MAIN LANGUAGE OF MEDICINE. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 1(7), 337-339.

27. Sharipov, B. (2023). SOME CONSIDERATIONS ON THE FORMATION OF CLINICAL TERMS IN LATIN. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(6), 477-479.

28. Sharipov, B. (2022). RETSIPROKLIK XUSUSIDA MULOHAZALAR. *Общественные науки в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования*, 1(19), 63-66.

29. Salimovich, S. B. (2022). RECIPROCAL SYMMETRY AND ITS GRAMMATICAL INDICATIONS. *EPRA International Journal of Research and Development (IJRD)*, 7(12), 129-131.

30. Salimovich, S. B. (2022). Studies of Reciprocity in Linguistics. *Eurasian Scientific Herald*, 8, 221-224.

31. Salimovich, S. B. (2023). TRANSLATION OF CLINICAL TERMS IN LATIN AND BASIC MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY CLASSES. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology*, 3(3), 100-103.

32. Bektoshevna, E. D., & Salimovich, S. B. (2023). LATIN AND GREC TERMINOLOGY IN THE PROCESS OF STUDY OF OPERATIVE SURGERY. *Yangi O'zbekistonda Tabiiy va Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar respublika ilmiy amaliy konferensiyasi*, 1(6), 66-72.

33. Nasimjanovna, K. F., & Salimovich, S. B. (2023). NAMES OF DISEASES AND THEIR USE IN CLINICAL TERMINOLOGY. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(6), 469-474.

34. Salimovich, S. B. (2022, January). FUNCTIONS OF LANGUAGE UNITS. In *Conference Zone* (pp. 62-63).

35. Salimovich, S. B. (2023). ESSENTIAL COMMENTS ON THE CHARACTERISTICS DUE TO THE ORIGIN OF CLINICAL TERMS AND FEATURES OF CLINICAL TERMINOLOGY. *Research Focus International Scientific Journal*, 2(6), 144-148.